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Exploring Parental Involvement Practices of Child Rearing In Five Major Cities of Nepal

Abstract: Child rearing in Nepali families has evolved with parents getting aware about more scientific method of child rearing. However, the traditional child rearing practices is still dominant in majority of Nepali families. Father's role has not been so significant during delivery and as well as prior to it. Present families with the parents' age in the range of 25 to 40 years have adopted various types of parenting along with traditional practices. In this work, prevalent types of modern parenting styles along with how they have taken common traditional practices of child rearing have been assessed in five major cities of Nepal, namely, Itahari, Udayapur, Kathmandu, Butwal and Pokhara. Thirty-five questions were developed on the basis of Alabama Parenting Questionnaire (APQ 1991). Based on this, parents were interviewed and scores were assigned to each answer. Standard scores for authoritative, authoritarian, permissive and traditional parenting styles were generated for each parenting scores with process of division by number of corresponding questions associated with each type of parenting. Then, data were processed using MS Excel. All the cities were observed to have more than sixty percent of families who have adopted authoritative parenting style and less than ten percent were found to be in permissive parenting domain. However, all categories of parenting have constantly continued their traditional practices as well.

Keywords: Authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, quantitative, parenting, culture, pregnancy, postnatal, Nepal

Introduction

Child rearing preparations start right from the time a woman is pregnant. The APA dictionary of Psychology has defined child rearing practice as a pattern of raising children that is specific to a particular society, subculture, family, or period in cultural history. Relating with this understanding, the child rearing practice thus clearly varies depending on the community, society and the geographical region. When a woman gets pregnant, the whole family participates in the child rearing process. The methods of child rearing in Nepali

families have evolved with parents getting aware about more scientific method of child rearing. However, the traditional child rearing practices is still dominant in majority of Nepali families.

Baumrind's (1967) seminal work on the classification of parenting styles has been essential in influencing research on parenting and its effect on children and adolescents. In her work she identified three types of parenting styles: authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive. According to her, authoritative parenting which comprises emotional support, high standards, appropriate autonomy granting, and unequivocal, and bidirectional communication has been shown to help children and adolescents develop an instrumental competence distinguished by the balancing of societal and personal needs and responsibilities (Baumrind, 1989, 1991a; Darling & Steinberg, 1993). Of those three types of parenting, authoritative parenting has more positive impact on children. Authoritative parenting (high acceptance, supervision, and psychological autonomy granting) leads to better adolescent school performance and stronger school engagement (Steinberg et al., 1992). Similarly, authoritarian parenting is somehow strict category of parenting.

Authoritarian is strict pattern of parenting in comparison to authoritative where children's perspective is not valued. Authoritarian parenting is characterized by demandingness, high expectations for conformity and compliance with parental authority, often associated with families that use physical punishment (Valentino, Nuttall, Comas, et al., 2012). Similarly, permissive parenting is the third type of parenting where parents care for their children with a friend-like gesture.

During pregnancy, delivery, and postnatal caring

A traditional Nepali family has a certain process while a woman is pregnant. It starts from the diet pattern of the mother. The mother gets to eat home based traditional food. However, most of the traditional Nepali families have a great objection with consumption of honey during pregnancy. There is a notion that consumption of honey leads to miscarriage.

Similarly, on the eighth month of pregnancy, the family organizes a *dahi-chiura* ceremony for the mother to be. In the ceremony the mother is fed beaten rice with yoghurt. The family also prepares food items that are the mother to be's favorites. In this occasion, the family members shower the mother with gifts especially for the upcoming child. This tradition is a preparatory step for arranging the immediate necessary items for the baby yet to be born.

In a traditional Nepali family, a father's role is minimum while a mother is pregnant. Even during the time of delivery, the father is not allowed in the delivery room. Immediately after delivery, as per the traditional belief, the umbilical cord is immediately cut off and the mother and the children are not touched by anyone until the naming ceremony of the baby that takes place on the 11th day after the birth. Until the 11th day, even the father is not allowed to touch the child and the mother which is one of the reasons that the emotional attachment lacks among child and the father. However, on the naming ceremony, father's role remains dominant while the mother's role is non-existent.

The diet of the mother also changes in the postnatal stage. The mother is fed with thyme seed soup, rice cooked in ghee and meat stew (chicken/mutton). Additionally, the mother is not allowed to have any green

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vegetables and is provided with soup-based food with a belief that the more soupy things the mother consumes, the more milk she would produce for the baby. Along with this, she is also provided with a special diet called *Sutkeri masala* that is a high calorie food prepared combining 32 different ingredients. As this food is high in calorie, it provides energy to the mother, and is also believed to tighten the muscles of the mother's body that gets loosened up during pregnancy.

A new born baby is wrapped in warm clothes head to toe regardless of the season soon after the birth. At home, the parents/guardians also put on kohl produced by burning fenugreek seeds along with oil. Similarly, to keep the child's room warm, the family arranges room heating by burning coal in the room. The smoke and its harm is not thought upon in this process as the major focus remains on keeping the baby warm. This, however, has an adverse effect on the child's health. During daytime, oil massage is provided to the baby under direct sunlight which again has a great effect on child's health.

Child is not fed anything other than milk until the rice feeding ceremony that is organized six months after the birth in case of son and in five months in case of daughter. These traditional aspects of child rearing practices have adverse effects in the growth and development of children.

Introducing diet

As mentioned above, a new born daughter is introduced to solid food on the fifth month of her birth and a new born son is introduced to solid food on the sixth month of his birth. In both the ceremonies, the child is provided with high calories foods which are especially high in carbohydrates. The major staple diet of Nepal, rice is introduced to the children in along with *lito* (a multi nutritional powder made by crushing multi-grains like maize, wheat, rice, oats, chickpeas and many more into fine powder). The child is also then gradually introduced to vegetables.

As the child turns into toddler, the diet then slowly changes from semi liquid to solid diet. This is the stage where child gets to eat rice as major diet. Along with the solid food, the child also gets to eat vegetables and proteins like eggs and meat. The family also focuses on feeding milk to the child on daily basis.

Introducing culture

Following culture is one of the important aspects of a traditional family. As the child gradually grows up from the toddler stage, the family then introduces the child to certain disciplines like greeting, respecting and hygiene. The elders make the child greet the elder members in the family with more respect. Along with this, the family also introduces the family relationship to the child and the degree of respect to be given to each member. In case of teaching discipline, the child is then taught to eat by himself/herself, taught to use the pot or the toilet and so forth basic discipline is introduced to the child along with the cultural introduction. As the child comes to the age four or five, then the parents admit the child in schools.

Generally, a traditional Nepali family follows the authoritarian parenting pattern in case of a newborn. The parents and in fact the whole family is overprotective regarding the newborn child. Since the child does not

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know anything and cannot express anything, it is the parents and the family members who make the decision for the child. The best part of this traditional child rearing practice is that child is provided enough care regarding the diet. The child is always the focus in such practice and at the same time, the mother gets completely shadowed after the delivery of the child which possibly pushes the mother into the stage of post-partum depression. However, the relationship dynamics of a family is questionable in such parenting as the father does not have much role to contribute to the child rearing.

This research is conducted to identify the types of parenting found in Nepal. Since Nepal is a country with a huge cultural diversity, culture and tradition play a great role to influence the parenting practice. However, the child rearing practice starts right from the pregnancy and thus there are stages of child rearing and parenting from the time the couples get pregnant.

Methodology

The sample survey was carried out in five major cities in Nepal. They are Itahari, Udayapur, Kathmandu, Butwal and Pokhara. Some parents were also contacted via cell phones due to Covid-19 emergency. The consent of approval was taken from each of the respondents before their interviews. The sites of data collection have been shown in the political map of Nepal below:

Figure 1 Survey sites in map of Nepal

The researchers developed their set of questionnaires in Nepali language adapted from base of Alabama Parenting Questionnaire (APQ-1991). Total 35 questions that assessed types of parenting as well as Nepal's typical traditional practices were put in random orders. Eleven questions were related to assessment of authoritative parenting to form authoritative scores, six questions were there to assess the authoritarian parenting to form authoritarian score.

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Three questions in the set assessed the permissive style to form permissive score and five questions had been adjusted to examine the traditional ways of parenting to form traditional score. Remaining questions were aimed for quality cross check of the respondents' answers. The responses that failed in quality cross check during the validation process were eliminated from further processing of data. Each question was adjusted with five options for answer and the respondent had to choose one of them. Highest and lowest score for each answer was set to five and one respectively.

Respondents from each city were selected for the interviews. They were in the range of 25 years to 40 years in age and had the education above high school. Each respondent has at least on child up to of eight years at their home. Responses were digitized to form standard authoritative score, standard authoritarian score, standard permissive score, and standard traditional scores dividing raw score of each category by numbers of questions related to define the category of parenting. Only twenty quality assured responses of respondents in each of above-mentioned cities were used in this study.

Results and Discussions

The data obtained in the research were analyzed using Microsoft Excel in MS 2020 package. The statistical results and the discussions have been presented city-wise in this section below

Kathmandu Valley

Twenty families from various cultures were selected from Kathmandu, Bhaktapur and Lalitpur to cover all ethnic diversity. Families chosen to have at least one parent as government or private job holder. The age range of parents was strictly maintained within 25 years to 40 years along with at least one ECD kid in each family.

Figure 2 Types of Family

Figure 3 Regression line

Figure 4 Regression line

Figure 5 Regression line Kathmandu Valley

The survey has shown that 75% of the sampled families have authoritative parenting 20% have adopted the authoritarian parenting while remaining 5% families have permissive parenting style. However, the traditional scores of each family are quite much high even up to 4.2 in average. This indicates that each type of family has continued the common traditional practices irrespective of their educational standard.

Chart 2 has indicated that the practices of following tradition in child rearing have increase along with the increment of standard authoritarian scores. More authoritarian parents tend to be more traditional with the positive correlation coefficient of 0.15. Chart 3 indicates that authoritative parents also increasingly followed the traditional rearing practices with relatively higher positive correlation coefficient of 0.35. This might be due to their cultural awareness of continuing their culture ahead as well. However, the permissive parenting styles have shown the negative correlation of 0.036 with the traditional rearing system.

The Udayapur City

This city has served as buffer between Terai and mountainous region of the country. Statistics of various types of parenting styles and their correlation coefficient have been in the graphs below:

Figure 6 Types of Family

Figure 7 Regression line of parenting

Figure 8 Regression line

Figure 9 Regression line

In this city, 79% of families have adopted the authoritative parenting style whereas there are only the traditional child rearing practice evaluated in this study was observed to be strongly depended on 17% in the category of authoritarian parenting and 4% have permissive child rearing practices. In addition to this, authoritative parenting score has negative co relation coefficient of 0.57 with traditional rearing practices which means parents in this category in Udayapur is more careful about their tradition as well. However, authoritarian, and permissive score have low positive correlation with the traditional scoring.

The Butwal City

Butwal city also enjoys the cultural diversity. People from the diverse part of our country reside in the city because of varieties of work opportunities. The statistical description of parenting practices obtained during this sampling study have been presented as following:

Figure 10 Types of family

Figure 11 Regression line parenting

Figure 12 Regression line

Figure 13 Regression line

There are 79% of families that follow the authoritative child rearing practices. Only 14% and 7% of people are observed to be authoritarian and permissive respectively in the rearing of their children. The traditional rearing practice has very low positive correlation with the increasing scores in authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive parenting styles. However, the average traditional score is 4.2 which indicates that most families have carried their traditional practices irrespective of their awareness in education, health and safety.

The Pokhara City

Pokhara is beautiful and modern touristic city in Nepal. People have modern lifestyle there. The statistical description of parenting practices obtained during this sampling study have been presented as following:

Figure 14 Types of family

Figure 15 Regression line

Figure 16 Regression line

Figure 17 Regression line

There are 60% of families that follow the authoritative child rearing practices. Only 35% and 5% of people are observed to be authoritarian and permissive respectively in the rearing of their children. The traditional rearing practice has very low positive co relation with the increasing scores in authoritarian and permissive parenting styles. The authoritative scores are negatively co-related with traditional practice score. However, the average traditional score is 3.9 which indicates that more families have carried their traditional practices irrespective of their awareness in education, health, and safety

Itahari city

This city is one of the biggest city that joins Dharan and Biratnagar. It is inhabited by people from diverse culture with very high economic ranges. The statistical description of parenting practices obtained during this sampling study have been presented as following:

Figure 18 Types of family

Figure 19 Regression line

Figure 20 Regression line

Figure 21 Regression line

There are 67% of families that follow the authoritative child rearing practices. Only 28% and 5% of people are observed to be authoritarian and permissive respectively in the rearing of their children. The traditional rearing practice has very low positive correlation with the increasing scores in authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive parenting styles. However, the average traditional score is 4.0 which indicates that most families have carried their traditional practices irrespective of their awareness in education, health and safety.

Conclusions

The table below summaries the significant attributes of child rearing practices in the cities as indicated by this sample survey research:

Table 1 Summary of data analysis

Cities	percentage of authoritative families	percentage of authoritarian families	percentage of permissive families	Correlation between traditional and authoritative score	Correlation between traditional and authoritarian score	Correlation between traditional and permissive score
Itahari	67	28	5	0.043	0.28	0.018
Udayapur	79	17	4	-0.57	0.26	0.15
Kathmandu	75	20	5	0.33	0.15	-0.036
Butwal	79	14	7	0.013	0.26	0.0077
Pokhara	60	35	5	-0.0319	0.078	0.0004

People in Pokhara, Kathmandu and Udayapur are in the verge of changing traditional practices as the traditional rearing practices have been observed to have negative correlation with modern rearing practices. Similar results were also produced in parenting study among Asian, European and American families

(Jambunathan et al., 2000). In contrast to this Butwal and Itahari have modern rearing practices are going side by side with the traditional rearing practices as indicated by positive correlation coefficient. In those cities, families are carrying their traditional practices irrespective of their modern rearing style. According to Das (2016), in his study about Punjabi families has also reported the similar trend. Common attribute in all the cities is having low value of correlation coefficient whether negative or positive. Seema & Begum, (2008) also obtained the similar result in south India as well. Report of (UNICEF, 2019) has also reported the slow and gradual child rearing practices in Nepal.

The limitations of the sampling survey study

In this study, standard parenting questionnaires were not used. The parenting questionnaires were compiled by the researchers themselves from many sets of rating scale sets. Only small numbers of respondents were accessed in each city and such small number of data may not be sufficient to make valid conclusions. The interview was conducted in short span of time using a mobile phone. While doing so the actual feeling and emotion of the respondents in many cases were not able to capture. The assessment was done with a single member in a family.

Conflict of Interest

The authors claim no conflict of interest in this research article.

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